

TO UNDERSTAND THE WHEEL-RAIL FLANGE SQUEAL THROUGH THE CONTACT PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract: This paper presents a study aiming at understanding the mechanism of wheel-rail flange squeal through the contact perspective. The study systematically demonstrates the connection between the observed wheel-rail flange squeal noise and contact force by measurements and numerical simulations. An integrated transient model enhanced by genuine 3D surface irregularities is developed. Features of flange squeal under four-speed levels corresponding to in-situ experiments are reappeared incorporating both global dynamics and local contact status. Generation mechanism of flange squeal is proposed by measurement observation and confirmed through the proposed model with multiple influencing key factors.

Keywords: Wheel-rail flange squeal; Wheel-rail contacts; Three-dimensional surface irregularities; Train-track dynamics modelling; Transient modelling; Mechanism comprehension.

1. Introduction

Wheel-rail squeal noise during train turning has been a tricky problem influencing passengers and nearby residents. The tonal curve squeal that mainly occurs in the inner rail has been extensively studied, while the broadband flange squeal that takes place in the outer rail that can be equally annoying is seldom mentioned and hardly investigated. Both kinds of squeal noise have been reported as random, occasionally or even 'erratic' because their occurrences can be influenced by dozens of factors, including the environmental conditions (such as weather conditions) at the very same observation locations, and the squeal can also be observed at a very low train speed. General noise controlling strategy, such as the speed controlling for rolling noise, is not effective for mitigating the squeal noise, and therefore, squeal noise control is still a challenge in front of the railway industry.

Extensive investigations on tonal curve squeal have largely attributed the curve squeal to two mechanisms, which are the falling friction mechanism [1] and the mode coupling mechanism [2]. The falling friction mechanism has revealed the curve squeal as a kind of instability caused by negative damping, which arises from the stick-slip feature of rolling contact, and mode-coupling mechanism provides explanations for ways of energy transfer between two different modes that are

theoretically orthogonal to each other, and the instability arises from non-conservative displacement-dependent friction forces even without the negative friction slope [2]. On the contrary, investigations on wheel-rail flange squeal detected from the outer rail are limited. Most of the existing publications regarding the broadband flange squeal is focusing on investigating its relation with the tonal curve squeal [3–5] and engineering practical mitigations [5–7] that lack fundamental mechanism analysis, a combined experimental and numerical investigations trying to comprehend the wheel-rail flange squeal mechanism is therefore desired.

To fill in the research gap, this paper proposes an integrated transient model, which can reappear the characteristics of flange squeal through a contact perspective. Three submodels, which are multi-body dynamic submodel, double curved-rail FE submodel, and Kalekr's 3D rolling contact submodel, are integrated into one coupled simulation system and are step-by-step validated with in-situ measurement. The characteristics of flange squeal with both flange squeal cases and non-flange squeal cases in the measurement conditions are finally reappeared by the validated transient model. Several critical factors regarding wheel-rail contact that induce flange squeal are discussed.

2. Measurement of flange squeal

Fig. 1 presents the experiment setup for the identification of wheel-rail flange squeal and the corresponding results with both flange squeal cases and non-flange squeal cases. The rail accelerations, rail-side noise were collected at the 1000 m radius of curvature operation line. The occurrence of flange squeal was identified through a combined analysis of rail accelerometers and the rail-side microphones with a 50 kHz sampling rate, where the flange squeal vibration was identified first by the accelerometers implemented on the outer rail, and then the occurrence of flange squeal noise was further confirmed with the rail-side microphones. To control the influential factors as much as possible, only one train was operated in the midnight metro line maintenance period, and the operating speeds were controlled as 40 km/h, 60 km/h, 80 km/h, 110km/h with repetitive runs to ensure the data reliability. A short-time Fourier transform was conducted then to generate the acceleration level and sound pressure level with a 0.1 s window length and 0.05 s signal overlapping from the measurement data. The analyzed frequency range is 0 ~ 20 kHz. The identified

flange squeal cases at the train speeds of 110 km/h and 80 km/h with intermittent broadband spectrums of both acceleration levels and sound pressure levels (Fig. 2 ((a)(b))) and non-flange squeal cases with the train speeds of 60 km/h and 40 km/h (Fig. 2 (right (c)(d))) are presented. Comparing the spectrum results of rail acceleration level and rail-side sound pressure level, it should be noted that even the flange squeal noise is not dominant compared with the overall sound pressure level

in the current case with a large radius of curvature (1000 m), the broadband and intermittent characteristics still exists, especially for the rail accelerations. Therefore, the flange squeal phenomenon can be effectively reflected through acceleration measurements (noted as flange squeal vibration) which are intensive and cannot be ignored, and this is also a reason why we develop a transient model to further analyze the underneath mechanism from the contact perspective.

Fig. 1 Experiment setup

Fig. 2 Flange squeal identification from spectrograms of lateral rail acceleration level (first row) and A-weighted sound pressure level (second row) (a) 110 km/h (b) 80 km/h (c) 60 km/h (d) 40 km/h

3. Model development

3.1. Submodels

In this section, critical steps for the development of a transient simulation model for flange squeal investigation at curved rail are briefly presented. The model consists of three submodels: multibody train dynamics submodel, Timoshenko beam curved rail submodel and the exact Kalker's 3D rolling contact submodel as the coupling component for the former two submodels. This model thus captures both the global multibody dynamic behaviours up to hundreds of meters scale and the local wheel-rail contact status down to millimetre level with a decent computational efficiency To well reproduce the flange squeals identified in the in-situ measurements, we attempted to recreate the real scenario by using genuine data as far as possible, including parameters achieved from the CAD drawing of the metro train in the test, and parameters from the test curved rail along with the

dynamic mobility results, and most importantly, the 3D wheel and rail surface information. The schematic diagram of the flange squeal simulation model is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Schematic diagrams of the proposed transient model

3.2. Model integration

Integration of three submodels into one flange squeal analysis model begins with the initial displacements of curved rail, wheel-rail contact pairs, and train vehicle that are generated statically. The gravity-induced rail permanent deformation is ignored by setting the initial equilibrium displacement of rail as zero. The contact approaching displacement is calculated by statically loading the gravity of the train on the rails. The train response is calculated by fixing the wheelsets first to calculate the spring compression distance and then adding the displacement of both curved-rail and contact approaching distance. It should be addressed that a static compatibility iteration is also conducted during the initialization process by calculating the three submodels

multiple times to finalize the initial condition that satisfies a good force equilibrium for all of the three submodels.

Dynamic iteration begins after decent system initialization. The time step which in general, is set as $dt = 1 \times 10^{-5}$ after balancing the convergence rate, computational cost, and accuracy. To solve the dynamic responses, the modal superposition methods based on theoretical impulse response function for curved-rail and the bathe integration method that is demonstrated to be more stable than a regular Newmark one [8] for multibody train model, are adopted.

The vehicle system, which is generated from the ‘set-in-right-position’ law based on the discipline of stationary total potential energy, needs to be reformulated when any one of the wheelsets operates on a new rail element. This is because the orientation of the track coordinate system keeps changing along the curved line. The vehicle response, for consistency, is also altered accordingly through the transformation function which serves as an initial condition for the next timestep.

Finally, the contact forces at one normal and two tangential directions, rail velocity, and displacement responses, and vehicle velocity and displacement responses are outputted as results of the simulation. The detailed simulation process is further demonstrated in Fig. 4. To realize the reappearance of flange squeal characteristics, genuine 3D wheel and rail profiles with surface irregularities are essential. Details of the irregularity measurements and the construction of 3D profiles will be elaborated in Section 4.1.

Fig. 4 Integration and simulation procedures of the proposed transient model

4. Model Validation

An on-site impact hammer test was conducted to validate the dynamic properties of the curved rail model. The element size is determined by a combined consideration of trail-and-test strategy and the criterion of one-sixth of

the concerned vibration wavelength (pin-pined modal frequency) [9]. The element sizes of 0.05 m, 0.1 m, and 0.3 m with 90 meters of double curved-rails models are developed (Fig. 5 (a)). It is shown that the frequency mobility ranging from 10 Hz to 2000 Hz is hardly

influenced when the element size is or below 0.1 m. In real circumstances, the rail is so long that most of the bending waves are not travelling back to the excitation point, while it is also impossible to establish a model with infinite length in numerical simulation. To find an optimized model length, the proposed curved-rail model is then established with a length of 30 m, 60 m, 90 m, and 120 m, where the simulated results show that a rail length above 90 m keeps consistent frequency mobility (Fig. 5 (b)). Therefore, the proposed curved-rail model is developed with a length of 90 m and an element size of 0.1 m. Comparing the measurement and numerical results (Fig. 5 (c)(d)), the calculated results of the proposed curved-rail model also fit reasonably well with the measurements in terms of vertical performance. For the lateral direction, the proposed model also delivers reasonable results in terms of the overall spectrum as well as the pin-pin resonant peaks for both the first-order and the second-order, although a discrepancy is observed for the lateral mobility at the 1340 Hz resonance peak. The discrepancy could be attributed to the web bending mode [10], where the Timoshenko beam element as an integrated bending-shear structure will inevitably neglect some higher-frequency local deformations. Despite this, the proposed model has shown a satisfactory performance for reflecting the coupled behaviours for flange squeal analysis, especially for the lower frequency parts that determine the existence of flange contact.

Fig. 5 Mobility of the curved rail FE model (a) element size discussion (b) model length discussion (c) vertical mobility validation (d) lateral mobility validation

4.1. Contact status assurance through the scanned wheel and rail profiles

The irregularities of two elastic contact surfaces have a significant influence on the contact forces. When

performing a contact simulation, the geometric surfaces are the most fundamental prerequisite. It is inevitable to generate inaccurate contact simulation results with an unrealistic wheel and rail profile (initially designed profiles change along with time because of wear, corrosion, etc.). Furthermore, as reported in [11], single-line 2D rail irregularities obtained from track measurement trolley may generate great differences due to different choices of measurement points at the rail cross-section, while general measurement systems are taken for not only rail but also wheel according to the nominal contact positions [12,13], and this may cause discrepancies for wheel-rail contact simulation in the train turning condition. To overcome this issue, instead of solely using an artificial irregularity with power spectral densities (PSD) or a track corrugation measurement trolley that captures the single-line 2D short-wavelength irregularities, real 3D wheel and rail surface irregularities have been used as input for contact simulation in this study. A 3D laser scanner (HandySCAN BLACK|Elite, AMETEK, Inc.) with featured function of capturing 3D point cloud data, was applied on-site for obtaining the short-wavelength rail and wheel surface irregularities of the test train wheels and rails. The 3D scanner has a nominated scanning accuracy of 25 μm when treating a diameter measurement on traceable sphere artifacts (ISO 17025 [14]). However, its capability of capturing the surface irregularity is not well documented, while Affatato et al. [15] demonstrated that this kind of device could achieve an accuracy of at least 10 μm for scanning a volume of 60 \times 50 \times 50 mm. Hence, short-wavelength irregularities ranging from 10 mm to 1000 mm are adopted in the following simulation according to the accuracy reference of a typical corrugation measurement trolley (RMF-1100 [16]).

The experiment setup, initial point cloud data results, and processed wheel-rail profiles and irregularities are presented in Fig. 6, which is used to generate the cross-sectional wheel and rail profiles for calculating the potential contact area with an initial coordinate system parallel to the corresponding track coordinate system. 3D wheel and rail surface irregularities are also generated from the scanned point cloud data under a three-dimensional interpolation. To balance the computational cost and accuracy, the interpolation is conducted with a spatial gap of 1 mm after 5 mm of filtering interpolation. wheel and rail surface features such as the nominal radius contact band on wheel and $\lambda \approx 40$ mm corrugation on rail and have been successfully captured, demonstrating the data reliability.

Fig. 6 Point cloud data and generated wheel and rail three-dimensional surface irregularities

Due to the high precision 3D scanner scanned over a limited length of both rail and wheel, the medium- and long-wavelength rail irregularity (1 ~ 100 m wavelength) information, which could influence the contact positions, is missing. To overcome this problem, the PSD spectrum from the China Academy of Railway Sciences (CARS)

was adopted here to generate the irregularity history with a wavelength from 1 ~ 100 m with a sampling rate of 0.5 m. Further SPLINE interpolation strategy is adopted before being implemented to the flange squeal simulation system (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 Rail irregularity with wavelength 1 ~ 100 m (a) vertical (b) lateral

4.2. Coupled validation of the proposed flange squeal simulation model

Kalker's rolling contact model by variational approach is widely accepted as a detailed and 'exact' contact simulation strategy. The contact simulation solver adopted in this paper has also been validated with the Manchester wheel-rail contact benchmark [17], where the validation process can be found in [18]. The benchmark process will not be presented in this paper for brevity. Given a validated contact stress prediction solver, the accuracy of the wheel-rail contact simulation results can be ensured through realistic and detailed geometry inputs for the contact surfaces. Therefore, the contact simulation result in our model is further ensured by the corresponding wheel and rail surface point cloud data that captures detailed geometry information which has been presented.

Due to the difficulties in a direct measurement of the high frequency wheel-rail contact force, the simulated rail accelerations from the integrated transient model with the well-validated rail submodel (section 4.2) serve as an intermediate product to validate with the measured rail

accelerations. Considering the available frequency range of a Timoshenko beam element, rail vibration results at a nearby measurement location (under corresponding wheel-rail profiles and rail mobility) without the extremely high frequency component are used to ensure the reliability of the simulated wheel-rail contact force by the rail responses.

In the time domain (Fig. 8), the simulated rail acceleration at both wheelset passing instants and between wheelset passing periods are at the same magnitude levels as the measured ones. In frequency domain (Fig. 9), the simulated spectrums have relatively consistent trends with the measured results, especially, three spectrum peaks around 600 Hz, 1100 Hz, and 1600 Hz are successfully captured by the proposed model. A reasonable consistency is achieved, which specifically confirms the reliability of the proposed transient model in terms of effectively relating the wheel-rail contact force output with the coupled system dynamics and the contact surface irregularities as inputs.

Till the end of this step, the connection between flange squeal vibration and the flange squeal excitation force as

the squeal source is fully revealed. The validated model can now be applied to conduct a mechanism comprehension for the wheel-rail flange squeal through a

contact perspective. The characteristic reappearance of flange squeal and corresponding parameter case studies are presented subsequently.

Fig. 8 Validation of rail accelerations at speed 83 km/h (23.06 m/s) (a) measured vertical acceleration (b) measured lateral acceleration (c) one-second validation of vertical acceleration (d) one-second validation of lateral acceleration

Fig. 9 Spectrum validation of rail accelerations at speed 83 km/h (23.06 m/h) (a) vertical (b) lateral

5. Characteristic reappearance and mechanism comprehension for flange squeal

Considering the broadband and intermittent features of wheel-rail flange squeal noise, a specific type of impulse excitation having the same features is thought to generate the flange squeal. Based on this point of view, a global-to-local analysis and a parameter discussion are presented in this section to elaborate on where does the impulse excitation (flange squeal) come from.

Characteristic reappearance of experimental flange squeal cases and non-flange squeal cases (refer to Section 2) is conducted through the validated model in section 5.1. The global contact forces induced by the coupled dynamic behaviours and the contact stress distribution inside the local contact patch are step-by-step presented and comprehensively discussed. The operation speed is set according to the experiment conditions as 110 km/h (27.7 m/s), 80 km/h (22.2 m/s), 60 km/h (16.7 m/s), 40 km/h (11.1 m/s). Conclusions are drawn to explain the generation mechanism of flange squeal from the contact perspective.

5.1. Characteristic reappearance of the flange squeal

The global-to-local analysis based on the proposed model is presented in Fig. 10 to Fig. 14 for flange squeal reappearance in correspondence to the in-situ experiment operation conditions. In Fig. 10, the train velocity is found to be one of the most important global factors inducing the flange squeal in this large radius of curvature

case. The impulse-like lateral contact forces reach 107 kN for 110 km/h at $T=0.459$ s and 97 kN for 80 km/h at $T=0.631$ s. Similar peaks can also be found for the vertical contact forces, while the impulse-like feature is not as distinctive as the lateral ones do. For the lower speed cases (60 km/h and 40 km/h), the impulse-like feature deteriorates drastically, although both vertical and lateral contact force peaks can still be found at $T=0.815$ s with lateral force peak of 39 kN for the 60 km/h case and $T=1.22$ s with lateral force peak of 24 kN for the 40 km/h case.

The broadband intermittent feature is the most fundamental characteristic for the flange squeal and therefore can be used as a primary indicator in the characteristic reappearance. A short-time Fourier transform was conducted for the transient contact forces to identify the occurrence of flange squeal (Fig. 11). The spectrograms reflect obvious flange squeal characteristic with broad-band spectrums at $T=0.4 \sim 0.55$ s and $T=1.0 \sim 1.15$ s for 110 km/h and $0.55 \sim 0.75$ s for 80 km/h, especially for contact forces in lateral direction. It is well known that the broadband features are induced by the impulse-like transient contact forces, and this kind of spectrum begins to deteriorate and become incomplete for $T=1.4 \sim 1.6$ s at 80 km/h and cases of speed levels as 60 km/h and 40 km/h. The deterioration of the broadband excitation feature can therefore preliminarily be attributed to the influence of train operation speed. Since a lower speed level cannot establish a force peak within a

very short period (impulse-like contact force), which induces the disappearance of flange squeal.

Fig. 10 Transient contact forces of the front outer wheelsets 110 km/h (b) 80 km/h (c) 60 km/h (d) 40 km/h

Fig. 11 Spectrogram of the vertical (first row) and lateral (second row) contact force at front outer wheel (a) 110 km/h (b) 80 km/h (c) 60 km/h (d) 40 km

The train operation speed accompanying the medium- and long-wavelength irregularities influence the wheel-rail contact positions in a curved rail line. Wheel and rail contact positions (Fig. 12) and the irregularities at the contact point with corresponding RMS of irregularities are presented (Fig. 13) to further analyse the relationship between flange squeal and contact positions as well as contact surface irregularities. Here, the contact position is described in the wheel profile coordinate system and rail profile coordinate system respectively. For the cases with flange squeal (110 km/h and 80 km/h), the impulse-like contact force occurs at the contact positions $y_{wp} = -33$ mm for the wheel profile coordinate and $y_{rp} = -25$ mm for the rail profile coordinate. In comparison, for $T = 1.4 \sim 1.6$ s at 80 km/h, the contact positions are located at $y_{wp} = -29.4$ mm and $y_{rp} = -21.6$ mm. For the cases without flange squeal, the contact positions are $y_{wp} = -30$ mm, $y_{rp} = -22$ mm for 60 km/h and $y_{wp} = -28$ mm, $y_{rp} = -20$ mm

for 40 km/h. The disappearance of flange squeal is found to correspond to the reduction of short-wavelength surface irregularities (to be discussed in the next paragraph) and the disappearance of wheel-rail flange contact, which will be further confirmed in the later local contact patch discussion.

Fig. 14 presents both the wheel and the rail irregularities in three wavelength ranges (10-30 mm, 30-100 mm, and 100-1000 mm) for the observed contact positions. For the rail, the wheel-rail flange contact region shows larger irregularities (RMS around $3 \sim 4$ μm) compared with the wheel-rail thread contact region (RMS around $2 \sim 3$ μm) in the wavelength 10-30 mm. The corrugation region ($y_{rp} = -8$ mm) shows an obvious increase in the irregularity (RMS around 8 μm) at wavelength 30-100 mm, which corresponds to the observed corrugation wavelength $\lambda \approx 40$ mm (Fig. 6). A similar feature is found for the wavelength 100-1000 mm (RMS around 15 μm). As for the wheel, the surface irregularity variations are more

drastic compared with the rail one, especially for those within wavelength 10-30 mm. For a flange contact region with $y_{wp} = -33$ mm, the RMS of irregularities at wavelength 10-30 mm can increase to 35 μm , while for the region around nominal radius point (or wheel-rail thread contact area), the RMS of irregularities is below 3 μm . For the wavelength 30-100 mm, a similar variation is obtained, with RMS of irregularities around 20 μm for flange contact region, and RMS irregularities below 3 μm for thread contact region. The irregularity variation becomes mild for the wavelength range 100-1000 mm, with RMS of irregularities around 20 μm for flange contact region, and RMS irregularities around 4 μm for thread contact region.

Jointly considering the wheel-rail contact positions and the measured wheel-rail surface irregularities, the

impulse-like contact force (flange squeal indicator) is most likely to be caused by the wheel surface irregularities, especially for those within wavelength 10-100 mm. Moreover, a higher speed tends to cause a deeper flange contact, which consequently alters the contact point from a low surface irregularity region to a much higher surface irregularity region and thus causes the impulse-like contact force. The measured high irregularity levels in these regions are considered to be caused by occasional and abnormal contacts (e.g., wheel-rail scratch) during train turning. Further studies on this fundamental wear problem are preferred to confirm this thinking, but it is not within the scope of this research. Here, we continue to investigate the cause of flange squeal by having a more detailed view within the contact patch to figure out how contact formulates during flange squeal.

Fig. 12 Contact positions at speed (a) 110 km/h (b) 80 km/h (c) 60 km/h (d) 40 km/h

Fig. 13 irregularities and RMS at contact positions for (a) wheel surface and (b) rail surface with wavelength 10-30 mm (1st row), 30-100 mm (2nd row), and 100-1000 mm (3rd row)

Contact patch acts as a box-window filter when treating short wavelength wheel and rail surface irregularities, this behaviour is named as contact filter effect [11]. A closer analysis for the 110 km/h case with flange squeal is presented to reveal the three-dimensional contact status of initializations, developments, occurrences, and

terminations process for the flange squeal (Fig. 14). It is not strange to find that, instead of an impeccably elliptical contact patch that is generally assumed in Hertz contact theory, the measured wheel-rail profiles lead to an irregular patch even at the initialization instant (Fig. 14(a)). This can be attributed to the wear of both wheel

and rail surfaces along with the train operation time. When the train begins turning, the contact patches move to the rail inner gauge side, with patch separation and a shrinking trend of contact patch size (Fig. 14(b)). The wheelset continues to move outward, where the flange contact begins to initialize with increasing lateral contact force and smaller contact area (Fig. 14(c)). During flange squeal, the contact patch tends to keep moving outward causing further slender flange contact, and is finally confined by the drastically increased lateral contact stiffness due to the geometrical shape between wheel flange and rail inner gauge. It is commonly known that great stiffness tends to cause a force peak because of the high sensitivity of displacement and force relationship at the flange contact position. Fig. 14(d)(e) show the contact patch during flange squeal. The wheel-rail flange contact formulates a much slender contact area compared with the regular thread contact position as an elliptic-like patch. This shrinkage of the contact area potentially impairs the contact filter effect, which may serve as an additional reason for causing flange squeal. Finally, Fig. 14 (f) shows an enlargement of the wheel-rail contact patch, which then theoretically increases the contact filter effect,

meanwhile, the wheel and rail surface irregularities reduce to moderate levels.

The above analysis within the contact patches covers the overall process of flange squeal. Contact filter effect and creepages are both identified as additional factors influencing the flange squeal. They interact with the previously identified wheel-rail surface irregularities and are indirectly influenced by the train operation speed that determines the contact positions. Given the complicated mutual effects or reverse effects among various factors, a comprehensive parameter analysis is desired. For example, a global sensitivity analysis, which could incorporate statistical parameters, is an optimum choice to further identify the sensitivity of all factors on flange squeal, this process remains infeasible for the current integrated transient model due to the extreme computational cost when treating dozens of statistical parameters. Therefore, we confine ourselves to the aspect regarding irregularities, which were deemed as the most fundamental reason inducing impulse-like contact force. Clarifications on how medium- and long-wavelength rail irregularity and short-wavelength wheel and rail surface irregularities can cause the flange squeal, are presented in [19].

Fig. 14 The 110 km/h outer wheel contact patch location (a) contact initialization (b) transferring to flange contact (d) initializing flange contact (d) flange squeal 1 (e) flange squeal 2 (f) end flanging

6. Conclusions

This paper presents a research effort attempting to understand the generation mechanism of wheel-rail flange squeal from the measurement phenomenon to the underlying source (contact force), which to the authors' best knowledge, is for the first time conducted on flange squeal.

A series of well-controlled in-situ experiments were carried out on an operating metro line. The intermittent, broadband, and extremely high frequency flange squeal

vibration and noise were successfully captured from the in-situ experiments.

A transient model consisting of three submodels was developed and integrated to numerically reappear the characteristic of flange squeal in the form of contact force. The proposed model intakes realistic in-situ experiment parameters, as well as genuine wheel and rail profiles generated from in-situ 3D scanning data of surface irregularities as inputs to best simulate the real scenario. With a combined measurement discussion and

comprehensive model validation, the generation of the flange squeal noise phenomenon is step-by-step connected to the flange squeal rail acceleration and finally to the wheel-rail contact force as the phenomenon-to-source analysis.

Flange squeal characteristic reappearance simulation and parameter study regarding irregularities are then conducted under the conditions of the in-situ experiment to give a detailed mechanism comprehension from the global aspect concerning coupled train dynamics to the local wheel-rail contact status. Specific findings are listed as follows:

1. The railway operation speed and medium- and long-wavelength rail irregularity are identified as two of the dominant factors that cause flange contact, which is the prerequisite of flange squeal;
2. Slender contact patch size is detected in the flange contact region, which theoretically induces a greater sensitivity of contact force to the short-wavelength wheel and rail surface irregularities. Therefore, the deterioration of contact filter effect is another reason for flange squeal;
3. Larger surface irregularity levels at the wheel flange and rail inner gauge have been confirmed through the in-situ experiment. They are found to be responsible for the generation of impulse-like contact force and broadband spectrum feature (flange squeal) with the occurrence of flange contact.

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As an overall concluding remark, the generation mechanism of wheel-rail flange squeal is attributed to existence of impulse excitation. The impulse excitation is generated through the wheel-rail flange contact where higher level surface irregularities exist at these contact regions. To be more straightforward, the broadband and intermittent wheel-rail flange squeal can be caused by an intensive rubbing between two contact surfaces with a transition from a lower level short-wavelength irregularity region to a higher level one.

It should be admitted that this research serves as an initial attempt for understanding the generation mechanism of flange squeal. Many more investigations are still needed, such as how do impulse excitation interact with wheel and rail high frequency modes? and which contact point is more likely to excite modes that are likely to radiate noise efficiently [20]? Complementary explanations or alternative theories may be found after incorporation of more and more relevant dynamic systems. Further investigations that can achieve flange squeal prediction are also being conducted (considering additional dynamic systems, such as wheel and rail modal dynamics, difference radius of curvature, noise radiation part, etc.). A comprehensive sensitivity index of more relevant influential factors for the wheel-rail flange squeal is expected in the future.

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